

Contextualizing the Overviews of PID Provider and Types

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Deliverable	D4.1 Contextualizing the Overviews of PID Provider Types

About

[PID4NFDI](#) is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure ([Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur – NFDI](#)). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through [Base4NFDI](#).

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Background

PID4NFDI¹ is a foundational service for persistent identifiers (PIDs) being developed for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI – Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur²). Funded as part of Base4NFDI,³ the project seeks to establish a sustainable and robust framework for PIDs within the NFDI ecosystem. Work Package 4 focuses on analyzing and documenting the governance, business, and license models of various PID providers and types, including an assessment of their risks and corresponding mitigation strategies using frameworks like POSI. This effort prioritizes models from project partners and other widely used PID services identified in earlier analyses within Work Packages 1 and 2.

The insights gained will inform the development of a decision model during the integration phase of PID4NFDI (beginning in January 2025), designed to evaluate the benefits, challenges, and costs of different PID approaches tailored to the diverse use cases within the NFDI consortia. The following document provides context for the data compiled in the overview of PID providers and types,⁴ with both forming **Deliverable 4.1** of PID4NFDI during the initialization phase.

Building on this foundation, Work Package 4 also aims to develop a concept for sustainable PID registration workflows that align with the NFDI's governance and funding structure. By identifying organizational and financial gaps and opportunities, the project will propose pathways to ensure the sustainable adoption of PID registration processes. The ultimate goal is to promote the strategic and long-term implementation of PIDs through sound governance, informed decision-making, and sustainable infrastructure. The concept is presented as **Deliverable 4.2**⁵ of PID4NFDI.

Introduction

This document outlines the conceptual and practical foundations for evaluating and selecting Persistent Identifier (PID) providers, focusing on the principles of openness, sustainability, and governance as defined by the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI)⁶. It provides context for the overview of the current

¹ <http://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/>

² <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>

³ <https://base4nfdi.de/>

⁴ PID4NFDI Overview of PID providers and types:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BvKmKij2WONCWheFTDnr2g3cGw3z5alZ9G2_qVCFpRk/edit?usp=sharing.

⁵ Hagemann-Wilholt, Kahlert (2024). D4.2 Concept for Sustainable PID Registration Workflows.

⁶ <https://openscholarlyinfrastructure.org/>; see also: Bilder, Lin, Neylon (2020). A detailed description of the POSI principles is given below.

landscape of PID providers and types (for a definition of providers and types see section *Entities/ Resource Types*), as compiled by the PID4NFDI project during its initial phase. The aim of this overview is to gather relevant data on PID providers and types to offer insights into transparent governance models, sustainable funding models, and interoperability – key criteria that underpin persistence and reliability. The gathered data is designed to serve as the foundation for a PID Selection Framework, enabling NFDI users to identify the most suitable PIDs for their specific use cases. Along with this contextualizing paper, this knowledge base will be published as a living document. Comments and suggestions from users for improvement of the data are highly welcome and will be integrated into the resource. The knowledge base allows comments from the NFDI community and beyond. It will be updated regularly as it expands and provides a dynamic resource that underpins the development of additional PID4NFDI service components and supports informed decision-making for integrating PIDs into diverse research infrastructures.

Overview of PID providers and types:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BvKmKij2WONCWheFTDnr2g3cGw3z5alZ9G2_qVCFpRk/edit?usp=sharing

Conceptual Background: POSI Principles

We used the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI) as a benchmark for evaluating sustainability efforts of PID providers. These concepts include essential principles and standards that provide the foundation for assessing the sustainability and efficiency of systems and processes in scientific infrastructure. They offer clear guidance to ensure that essential goals regarding transparency, accountability, and long-term preservation are achieved. These include e.g. the integration of transparent funding models, the establishment of responsible governance structures, and the continuous assurance of the technical functionality of systems. These benchmarks help monitor progress while ensuring the accountability of all involved parties.

The POSI principles provide guidelines to ensure that scholarly infrastructure remains open, sustainable, and independent. The principles are designed for organizations offering services to the scholarly community and emphasize transparency, accountability, and long-term viability. The POSI framework is organized into three key categories:

1. Governance

The aim is to maintain the infrastructure's independence and avoid conflicts of interest:

- **Openness:** The organization should operate transparently and be accessible to all stakeholders.
- **Independence:** It should be free from undue commercial influence or control.
- **Community-driven:** Decision-making should actively involve the broader scholarly community.

2. Sustainability

The organization must be designed for long-term viability:

- **Sustainable Funding:** It should have a stable business model that does not rely solely on short-term grants.
- **Financial Transparency:** Revenue and expenditures must be publicly disclosed to build trust.
- **Reinvestment:** Any surplus should be reinvested in the development and improvement of the infrastructure.

3. Insurance of Openness

Ensuring permanent access to knowledge and data is crucial:

- **Open Data:** The infrastructure should adopt open standards and data formats.
- **Long-term Availability:** Services and data must remain accessible to the scholarly community in the long run.
- **Interoperability:** Systems should be compatible with other open infrastructures.

The POSI principles are particularly significant in a landscape where many scholarly tools and platforms are at risk of commercial takeover or influence. Adherence to these principles helps ensure that infrastructures serve the needs of scholarship and remain resilient against external pressures.⁷

Method: Rationale for Category Selection

The following section describes the primary criteria used to assess PID providers, based on which data were collected, and explains their selection for subsequent use. These criteria were chosen to provide a holistic view of PID providers,

⁷ See also de Castro et al. (2023) on economic risks and factors promoting trust in PID systems, pp. 40, 45-55.

focusing on both technical capabilities and organizational sustainability. They allow for a systematic comparison of providers, enabling stakeholders to identify solutions that best fit their needs while aligning with Open Science principles. By evaluating governance, licensing, interoperability, and offered services, we ensure that the selected PID systems support reliable, long-term, and FAIR-aligned research practices.

Several PID overviews already exist, published or available online as registries, with others still in preparation (e.g. from the Canadian Research Knowledge Network⁸). For instance, the PID Services registry⁹, developed during the FREYA project and now maintained by DataCite, provides valuable information. A basic but comprehensive list from the Library of Congress (<https://www.loc.gov/standards/sourcelist/standard-identifier.html>) covers a quite complete list of identifiers that are applied in the library context. Similarly, but with a focus on the life sciences, is the Identifiers.org registry¹⁰ that allows registering and resolving different (P)ID types. Finally, the EOSC PID Policy and Implementation Task Force has published an overview of PIDs used in the EU, detailing names, websites, resource types, global resolvability, and including a comments section.¹¹

While these overviews offer important insights, they provide little or no information about business models, organizational stability, or other criteria aligned with the POSI principles. Such details are crucial for mapping to the requirements of NFDI consortia. Collecting this information is labor-intensive, requiring cooperation from PID providers and regular updates to reflect changes, including those driven by initiatives like PID4NFDI.

Entities / Resource Types

The selection of a suitable PID provider depends very much on the **entity or resource types** for which PIDs are to be allocated. Distinct types of resources often have unique requirements, **metadata schemes or standards**, and use cases. Ideally, PIDs and their metadata capture the resource-specific properties and offer the possibility of integrating community-specific requirements (e.g. linking with discipline-relevant metadata). In interaction with other PID systems, they then allow the mapping of more complex creation contexts for quality assurance and reproducibility of research results.

⁸ Carmichael, Aspler (2024).

⁹ <https://pidservices.org/>

¹⁰ <https://registry.identifiers.org/registry>

¹¹ Kálmán (2024).

Depending on the entity type, a number of providers have already been established in the field of (open) PID systems that offer PIDs for objects, persons or facilities. Other PID systems are still emerging. PID types, providers and entities to which PIDs are assigned are rarely in a one-to-one relationship: A **PID type** (e.g. ARK, DOI, ePIC PID) can be assigned to several **entities** (e.g. dataset, instrument) and might be offered by several providers (e.g. DataCite, Crossref). The **PID class** model, which summarizes the concept of type and entity, can be used to derive a recommendation model for PIDs. Additionally, a **PID provider** offers a service where an individual PID of a specific PID type – offered by the provider – in which this provider specialises can be minted, mostly combined with an entity/resource type. The combination of a PID provider, the offered PID type(s) and the assignable entities results in a **PID system**.¹²

The maturity of PID types is defined by whether, to what extent and the duration

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of PID class
(source: https://beta.pid-monitor.org/pid_class.html)

for which PIDs are assigned to specific entities. We find mature systems mainly where we have less dynamic activities in the descriptions of entities, e.g. in the area of already published resources or for persons and organisations. However, more and more requirements emerge in the area of the creation of early-stage and dynamic research resources and its provenance: e.g. in the generation and analysis of research data and software, instruments etc. used for this purpose. A comprehensive use of PIDs and standardised descriptions will result in a better understanding of the creation and development of research resources.¹³ Data on PID registration numbers and connected entities along with time data can therefore reveal fundamental insights into the maturity of the service and its reach.

¹² See definitions of Andreas Czerniak (PID Network Germany project) on PID class, type and entity at PID Monitor (Beta version): https://beta.pid-monitor.org/pid_class.html (to be launched in Q1/2025).

¹³ For a definition of maturity, an overview on the maturity of PID types and criteria for evaluation see Ferguson et al. (2018); Lavasa (2018), and Dasler et al. (2020).

The overview of entities/ resources types for our knowledge base to support the selection of potential PID providers is not final, but work in progress. However, when

Figure 2: Results from PID4NFDI Stakeholder Survey on Question “For which entities do you (want to) register PIDs?”

looking at potential PID services and providers for NFDI, we will focus primarily on those entities that were also categorised in our landscape analysis as currently and in future relevant by the respondents of our survey.¹⁴

Metadata and their schemata

Metadata schemata define the structure and rules for describing resources, ensuring consistent and meaningful metadata across systems. These schemata are closely tied to the types of resources they describe, such as datasets, samples, instruments, or software. The diversity of metadata schemata reflects the various needs of different disciplines and resource types - what works for describing a dataset may not be suitable for a software package or a physical specimen. Open and transparently documented schemata are essential to enable interoperability, ensuring that metadata can be understood and reused across systems, disciplines, and time, thus supporting the FAIR principles and the broader research ecosystem.

PID4NFDI's survey on PID usage highlighted the importance of metadata alignment to improve interoperability and efficiency in research workflows. Respondents noted that inconsistencies in metadata schemata often create barriers to the

¹⁴ El-Gebali et al. (2024). 1.1 Landscape of PID Practices.

integration of PIDs into cross-disciplinary systems. Aligning metadata practices, particularly for complex resource types like instruments and software, was identified as a pressing need to reduce redundancy and enhance data reusability. These findings emphasize the value of collaborative efforts to harmonize metadata schemata across PID providers and disciplines, ensuring seamless integration into diverse research ecosystems.¹⁵

Service Portfolio

A complementary and comprehensive service portfolio is essential for a PID provider to meet the diverse needs of its users effectively. **Test environments** allow institutions, repositories, and developers to experiment with PID integrations and workflows in a risk-free setting, ensuring smooth implementation before going live. A robust **helpdesk and support system** is critical for resolving technical issues, guiding users through complex processes, and providing expertise on best practices, particularly as PIDs are integral to research workflows. Detailed and up-to-date **documentation** empowers users and repository managers to understand and utilize the provider's tools and services independently, improving the learning curve and promoting efficient adoption. Finally, **analytics and metrics** enable users to assess the impact and usage of their PIDs, providing valuable insights for reporting, resource management, and demonstrating the reach of research outputs. Together, these features ensure that PID providers deliver not just identifiers but a reliable, user-focused infrastructure that supports the entire research lifecycle.

Governance

This criterion addresses the organizational structure, transparency, and financial sustainability of a PID provider. It includes aspects such as adherence to open governance principles and the financial models used (e.g., free access, membership fees). These factors are critical for assessing the long-term reliability and independence of a provider, as well as the risks associated with vendor lock-in or proprietary systems. The governance structure of PID providers ensures their operations are transparent, inclusive, and community-focused. Strong governance helps maintain sovereignty from external pressures and ensures the organization's commitment to serving the needs of the scholarly community.

Business Models

PID providers operate under various business models, which directly impact their sustainability and accessibility. These models generally fall into two broad categories:

¹⁵ El-Gebali et al. (2024). 1.1 Landscape of PID Practices.

1. **Free for All:** Some PID providers, such as **Wikidata IDs** or **ARK identifiers**, operate under open, cost-free models, making them highly accessible but potentially reliant on external funding or volunteer contributions.
2. **Membership and Fee-Based Models:** Others, such as DOI registries, adopt structured membership models where organizations pay an annual membership fee, in some cases alongside additional costs, such as PID registration costs. These fees contribute to the financial sustainability of the infrastructure and ensure that services remain available over the long term.

Practical Implications

For users, the primary consideration often lies in the **membership and fee models** offered by different providers. Institutions, libraries, and data repositories must weigh the cost structures against their needs, balancing affordability with the reliability and features provided. While cost-free options may seem appealing for smaller organizations or low-resource settings, membership models often offer added benefits, such as technical support, integration tools, and service guarantees.

Ultimately, the choice of PID provider involves not only immediate practical considerations but also a long-term commitment to supporting a robust and sustainable infrastructure. Researchers and institutions should remain mindful of how these models align with broader principles of openness, transparency, and reliability in scholarly communication.

Licensing

For the integration into NFDI, it is highly recommended to focus on PIDs and PID providers (e.g. PID systems) that support open licenses at least for the PID metadata to foster findability of entities. Proprietary PIDs come with different risks, such as lock-in effects or uncertainty of future costs. PIDs of proprietary providers such as Scopus Researcher or Affiliation ID do not fit the very idea of Open Science and therefore are not recommended for NFDI.

Figure 3: Answers of PID4NFDI survey on “Licenses Applied in Repositories and other Services”.

One result of our survey shows that most organizations use open licenses in their repositories. However, it remains important to examine the specific licenses used, as they are crucial for the reuse of research assets.

Sustainability

The sustainability of a PID provider refers to its ability to operate reliably over the long term, ensuring that the PIDs remain functional and accessible. This involves maintaining robust technical infrastructure, implementing a stable and transparent business model, and adapting to evolving technological and community needs. Additionally, it encompasses the durability of the minted PIDs, guaranteeing their continued usability and interoperability in digital research ecosystems, regardless of changes in the provider's operations or circumstances.

Interoperability

Interoperability among PIDs, metadata schemata, and PID providers is essential for creating a cohesive and flexible research infrastructure. Interoperability can be defined as 'the ability of data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort'.¹⁶ Using open systems minimizes dependencies on specific systems or vendors, thereby reducing the risk of lock-in effects. Through a robust technical base built on open standards and the availability of well-documented APIs, seamless integration and communication between systems can be enabled. Furthermore, the interconnectivity of PID providers, such as the integration of ORCID or ROR within other PID providers, ensures that diverse components of the research ecosystem can work together. By facilitating seamless collaboration and data exchange across platforms and providers, interoperability supports a sustainable, open, and FAIR-aligned research environment.

Main Results

The initial analysis of PID services has yielded key insights for the first draft of the PID services overview table. This table, currently a living document, serves as a foundational tool for the ongoing work of PID4NFDI and facilitates collaboration with other endeavours (see paragraph *Outlook*). While the table initially focused on the most widely used PIDs within NFDI, it is not yet complete and will be expanded both in scope and depth of information over time.

At present, the table includes basic information on approximately 17 PID services. These services vary significantly in the transparency of the information they

¹⁶ Wilkinson et al. (2016).

provide about their organizational structures, business models, and interoperability. While some providers offer detailed and accessible documentation, others present information that is scattered, challenging to locate online, or not available online at all.

In terms of business models, two main categories have been identified:

1. **Free or Institution-Supported Models:** Some PID providers, such as ROR, PIDA, w3id.org and ARK, operate free of charge, with costs often covered by institutions within the academic community.
2. **Fee-Based Membership Models:** Others, including DataCite, ORCID, and ePIC, utilize fee-based and/or membership-based models. Despite this, these providers generally adhere closely to the POSI principles and maintain non-commercial aspirations.

To ensure a more complete and transparent overview, the next steps involve contacting PID providers directly when critical information is unavailable online. This effort includes verifying the existence of missing details and encouraging their transparent publication.

Regarding licensing, our recent survey indicates that open licenses are widely used within NFDI, and most consortia have clear policies governing license usage for research data. This aligns well with Open Science principles. However, challenges remain with proprietary providers, whose conditions are often incompatible with these principles. As such, proprietary services have not been included in the PID provider overview.

NFDI should continue to prioritize Open Science by focusing on open licenses and transparency in PID services, ensuring alignment with its goals and values.

Taking the POSI principles as a reference, the interim result of the analysis of the available data is a mixed picture. While some data is still missing, some interim results can already be read from the existing data. While some PID providers disclose their governance structures and distribute sustainability across several shoulders, these issues are still unclear for other PID providers. However, this does not mean that they are less sustainable, but more transparency would be desirable in terms of building trust.

Outlook: Further Data Collection and Usage

We will continuously improve the knowledge base and fill the existing gaps by reaching out to PID providers. We have identified several reuse scenarios for the data:

In the DFG-funded **PID Network Germany project**,¹⁷ with which we collaborate on several aspects addressing both the interests of the NFDI community and stakeholders from the broader German research landscape, efforts have also been made to map the PID landscape by conducting a survey among German higher education and research organizations. In addition to the survey aimed at capturing PID management practices within institutional infrastructures at research organizations, an overview of PID types has been developed. The data collected in this context complements the information on PID providers gathered in the PID4NFDI initiative. The objective is to consolidate these two knowledge bases to enhance their explanatory value.

Within the PID Network project, this data serves as the foundation for the planned **PID Monitor**,¹⁸ which will extend the ORCID Monitor¹⁹ developed in the ORCID DE project.²⁰ Additionally, the project will produce a PID roadmap, potentially forming the basis for a national PID policy. We will work closely with the PID Network to align with this development and advance **NFDI-wide PID guidelines**, which will build on preliminary work derived from existing data on PID providers as well as the governance framework for sustainable PID management within NFDI (D4.2).²¹

Additionally, the data gathered from PID providers will be integrated into the **Cookbook Getting Started with PIDs**²² developed by PID4NFDI. This resource brings together essential information to help navigate the field of scholarly PID registration. The Cookbook aims to serve as an introductory guide, summarizing the key access points to information provided by PID providers.

A summary of the collected data is available in the **PID provider overview** on the PID4NFDI website.²³ This overview is designed to offer a quick and accessible introduction to the landscape of existing PID services, with concise descriptions and key links to further information on the providers' websites.

During the integration phase of the service, we plan to develop a **PID Selection Framework** to assist users of the PID Coordination Hub in identifying suitable PID providers that align with their specific use cases and requirements. This effort involves, among other aspects, encouraging PID providers to transparently disclose their governance structures and business models, making it easier for users to select appropriate PIDs.

¹⁷ PID Network Germany: <https://www.pid-network.de/en/>

¹⁸ PID Monitor (Beta Version): https://beta.pid-monitor.org/pid_class.html

¹⁹ ORCID Monitor: <https://monitor.orcid-de.org/en/index.php>

²⁰ ORCID DE Project (in German): <https://www.orcid-de.org/ueber-orcid-de/orcid-de-projekt>

²¹ Hagemann-Wilholt, Kahlert (2024). D4.2 Concept for Sustainable PID Registration Workflows.

²² PID4NFDI Cookbook: <https://pid4nfdi-training.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²³ PID4NFDI – Provider and Services: <http://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/get-pid/services-provider/>

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